

Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan

D6.1

Document Factsheet

Grant agreement	101086638
Call identifier	Horizon-CL6-2022-Governance-01-08
Project title	Urban ReLeaf: Citizen-powered data ecosystems for inclusive and green urban transitions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	48 months
Instrument	Horizon Europe
Type of action	Innovation action
Deliverable number	D6.1
Deliverable name	Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan
Work package	WP6: Dissemination, Exploitation and Strategic Communication
Task	T6.1: Develop, deliver, and update and Urban ReLeaf strategic engagement, communication, and dissemination plan
Deliverable lead	University of Dundee (UNIVDUN)
Deliverable type	Report
Due date	30/04/2023
Review completed	11/05/2023
Submission date (v1.0)	15/05/2023
Submission date (v1.1)	15/11/2024
Document version	1.1 (EC Approved)

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Acknowledgement

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Reference

Please cite this work as:

Woods, M., Veeckman C.(2023). Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan. D6.1 for the Horizon Europe and Innovate UK co-funded project Urban ReLeaf under grant agreements ID: 101086638, 10061290 and 10041792. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18266908.

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Short description	The first version of Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan is a comprehensive guide that defines the resources, planning and methods to communicate the project, its outcomes and activities to third parties and external stakeholders.
Keywords	Engagement; Dissemination; Communication; Storytelling; KPIs;

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the GA	
EU-R	Classified information - Restricted under EC Decision 2005/444	
EU-C	Classified information - Confidential under EC Decision 2005/444	

History			
Version	Date	Released by	Comment
0.1	28.03.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Draft structure v01
0.2	09.04.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Section 1
0.3	18.04.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Section 2 Outline
0.4	22.04.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Section 3 Outline
0.5	01.05.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Full Draft
0.6	02.05.2023	Carina Veeckman (VUB)	Section 1.4.4 and 1.4.5
0.6	03.05.2023	Gerid Hager (IIASA)	Draft review
0.7	04.05.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Addressed review comments
0.8	04.05.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Addition of Figures, Illustrative Use Case for Hub and Spoke social media
0.9	10.05.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Stakeholder Mapping, Conclusion, Formatting, Table and Figures
1.0	11.05.2023	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Final version for submission
1.1	12.11.2024	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN) Carina Veeckman (VUB)	Amended Table 1 hard to reach communities; stakeholder categories and target audiences (Tables 1 and 4); Stakeholders added in body text to explain Figure 2; Increased resolution Figures 3-6 were added; Updated Civic Groups; Explanation of communication action rationale 1.3.1; Explanation about the four-step recruitment process added; explanation added about the KPI min.50 female participants

Project Partners

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Acronyms

BGI	Blue Green Infrastructure
CBO	Community Based Organisation
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Electrotechnical Committee for Standardisation Operations
CIW	Climate Innovation Window
CO	Citizen Observatory
CoP	Community of Practice
CS	Citizen Science
DEI	Diversity, Equity and Inclusion
DfB	Design for Business
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ECD	Engagement, Communication and Dissemination
ECS	European Citizen Science
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EEA	European Environment Agency
EIE	Environmental Insights Explorer
EPA	Environment Protection Agency
ETSI	A European Standards Association
EU	European Union
EuroGEO	European Group on Earth Observations
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reuseable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Group on Earth Observations System of Systems
GIF	Graphic
ICC	Intelligent Cities Challenge
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KE	Knowledge Exchange
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS Teams	Microsoft Teams
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
R&D	Research and Development
RRI	Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIA	Systems Innovation Approach
SME	Small to Medium Enterprises
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable of the Urban ReLeaf project, which is co-funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101086638 and UKRI Innovate UK grant agreement numbers 10061290 and 10041792. The purpose of this document is to provide the initial version of the Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination (ECD) Plan. The objective of the ECD Plan is to act as a comprehensive guide for the Urban ReLeaf consortium to ensure that the overarching aims and objectives of the project are met, whilst creating an effective strategy to with the time and resources to maximize success.

The Urban ReLeaf project aims to engage with a range of different stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on engaging a diversity of people and hard-to-reach communities. To achieve this, our guidelines encompass different aspects of ECD, including activities that are planned and their scheduled delivery, as well as the tools, resources, materials, and channels available to support the core and distributed engagement and communication approach. We include a visual review of our collaborative approach to our strategy for communications, evidencing workshop activities undertaken to define and co-create key features for ECD with partners. Finally, we present a strategy for monitoring ECD, with a reflective process to iterate and improve our approach.

This deliverable comprises three parts:

Part 1: Describes an inclusive Communication and Engagement Strategy and defines the terms and phases of delivery along with key target audiences. The strategy includes the project values, key drivers and a framework for the use of storytelling for communicating activities, outputs and innovations. We outline our approach to inclusivity to encourage participation from a diversity of people and in addition, we include information on the project's green guidelines.

Part 2: Presents the Communication Tools and Dissemination Plan, which lists targeted communications and channels to be used for engagement and dissemination. We provide an exemplar of key messages, the tone and nomenclature to meet objectives and present an outline for the uptake of relevant activities. We also indicate a timeframe for promotion of all relevant activities, innovations and outputs with a focus on phase 1 and 2 of delivery.

Part 3: This section defines the approach to monitoring ECD and outlines subset of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with a guide to iteratively assess, reflect and adapt the plan where necessary. We also define the appropriate sustainability of the project developments both during and after the project end.

Introduction

The communication activities involve time and financial resources by the consortium partners. It is therefore essential to establish a concise communication strategy with a predetermined scope and carefully defined goals. This deliverable is part of the Work Package 6 Dissemination, Exploitation and Strategic Communication. WP6 objectives are to:

- Develop and deliver a strategic communications plan and approach to establish engagement, knowledge exchange, innovation outputs and dissemination for Urban ReLeaf activities
- Create excellent brand design to reinforce the project concept and values across all materials
- Ensure design, events and communications meet highest ethical standards, data governance principles, gender equality and inclusiveness values, and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) guidelines more generally
- Identify and nurture relationships with key projects, stakeholders, and networks to create high levels of visibility and leverage awareness for Urban ReLeaf activities
- Coordinate two Design for Business sprints to promote exploitation of key results

WP6 is a transversal work package (Figure 1) integrating the results of all the WPs for the Engagement, Communication and Dissemination process. The plan is designed to ensure effective communication and engagement with audiences throughout the project, as well as to disseminate project outputs and innovations to relevant stakeholders and can be learned from on a European scale.

Figure 1 Urban ReLeaf Interdependencies of Workpackages

In the first 24 months the plan builds on synergies with WP2 Stakeholder Dialogue and Inclusive Citizen Participation. It will integrate the communications plan with the participation journey for T2.2 Co-create inclusive strategies for the Urban ReLeaf pilots and T2.4 Reflections and insights workshops to communicate externally and ensure stakeholder engagement is inclusive. Furthermore, it will align with T4.1 Urban ReLeaf pilot action plans, iterations, and summaries to ensure communications will support plans for Urban ReLeaf City Pilots. The communication plan will support the recruitment of stakeholders for WP5 Community of Practice Working Groups.

This document is directly linked to Deliverable 6.4 Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination plan II in Month 28, which will provide the opportunity, to report and reflect on progress towards engagement communication and dissemination goals and specific KPIs and targets and refine the strategy for the latter phases of the project where necessary. It will also inform two iterations of the Outreach, Impact, and Exploitation report, namely Deliverable 6.3 in Month 24 and Deliverable 6.6 in Month 48.

1 Part 1: Engagement and Communication Strategy

1.1 Central Definitions

The Urban ReLeaf knowledge management process distinguishes between Engagement, Communication and Dissemination (ECD), and Exploitation, which is treated more specifically in bespoke deliverables outlined in the Introduction. The terms Communication and Dissemination are in line with the European Commission (EC) definitions¹. Urban ReLeaf will also engage, build, and maintain a strong relationship with specific actors and audiences throughout the project. Therefore, we add engagement as an additional term. We define these terms as part of the strategy as follows:

Communication

Communication measures to promote the project throughout the full lifespan of the project. The aim is **to inform and reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and the benefits the project** will have for citizens. It aims to reach audiences in an inclusive and accessible manner.

Dissemination

The **public disclosure of the results by appropriate means**, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.

and

Engagement

A **process of knowledge exchange** and creation to support co-creation objectives of the project pilots, to encourage and support audiences to become² active participants in the project and to foster a sense of ownership and empowerment among participants and communities towards the project. Urban ReLeaf pilot cities will follow and monitor an inclusive engagement strategy to engage a diversity of people.

1.2 Communication Phases

The planning and execution of the project Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination activities follows a schedule closely aligned with key project deliverables and milestones. This draft outline for dissemination channels and material will be refined throughout the duration of the project. In the initial phase we focus on building engagement through the concept, vision and expected outcomes of Urban ReLeaf research and innovation since no results are available yet. As results become available, we will communicate research outcomes and insights through our technical presentations and publications as new developments are achieved. The plan is broadly organised around 3 main phases:

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/other/events/20210609/1_intro2comm-diss-expl_en.pptx

²

Phase 1: Targeted media campaigning for awareness raising and mass mobilisation (M1–24). The first phase of the engagement, communication, and dissemination plan for Urban ReLeaf aims to ensure that relevant stakeholders and the wider public are aware of the project's vision, objectives, and expected results. We will build on our initial stakeholder mapping refine specific core project audiences for communication, engagement, and dissemination. As part of the communication plan, an identity, web presence, and social media channels will consolidate the ECD plan, values and vision. Information materials, such as brochures and posters, will be designed to support stakeholder awareness and engagement, and will be disseminated to various events.

For the city pilots, a bespoke approach to engage audiences around key activities will be developed, supported by the creation of a communication pack. Strategic communication storylines will be developed using a 'storytelling for two' approach (see 1.4.1). Similarly, we will work with Community of Practice working groups to define and map their core audiences according to the aims and objectives for each of the three topics.

Urban ReLeaf will apply an inclusive engagement strategy through a 4-step recruitment process. This approach includes the definition of key performance indicators for inclusive engagement with a general call with an open invitation to join, specific inclusion criteria relevant to the pilots' scope, and a targeted approach focusing on missing profiles and underrepresented groups through personal invitations and local partnerships with trusted intermediaries, such as community-based organizations. Multi-actor participatory workshops will be held to co-create inclusive strategies. The project's engagement and communication approach will be monitored and reflected upon using inclusive and green guidelines.

Early dissemination activities will take place within city pilots, engaging stakeholders to assess urban greening policy processes and identify citizen engagement opportunities. The project's publications and presentations will mainly describe the project's concept and research methodology.

Phase 2: Engagement, campaign communication and targeted dissemination (M13 – 36)

In the second phase, the ECD plan will concentrate on engaging and involving stakeholders in a targeted and inclusive manner to support their continued participation over time. The dissemination strategy will utilise a variety of media and channels to reach a diverse audience, including policymakers, industry partners, and the general public. The city pilots will develop storylines from phase 1 and highlight stories that showcase the experiences of individuals and participating communities in citizen science campaigns. The use of multimedia content will help to promote engagement with citizens on the topic of urban greening, increase awareness, and generate interest in environmental monitoring. Pop-up community and culture labs will be established in each city to bring the project's vision and results to life.

Throughout this phase, the project's results will be mapped iteratively, and the Community of Practice (CoP) Working Groups, Pop-up community and culture labs, and other relevant activities will be showcased. The website will be updated regularly to provide information about the project's initial results and future work, as well as to promote upcoming events, conferences, and workshops. The primary audience for the communication of results and publications will be the key stakeholders listed in Table 3. Press releases and mainstream press will be used to promote Urban ReLeaf adoption by policy, public, and research end-users through planned project outputs and outcomes. Analytics will be used to measure the effectiveness of the strategy, and the approach will be adjusted as necessary.

Phase 3: Intensive Dissemination and assessment period (M30 - 48) During the final phase of the project, we will employ targeted dissemination strategies to showcase use-cases, data, and insights across all pilot cities. Various stakeholder-appropriate messages and channels will be utilised, including events, scientific conferences, scientific publications, and workshops.

To promote the adoption of Urban ReLeaf outputs, press releases and mainstream media campaigns will aim to reach policy, public, and research end-users. The goal is to ensure that the project's outputs and outcomes are disseminated to all stakeholder groups before the end of the funding period.

This phase will involve significant effort, including insight workshops in six pilot cities, a project video with participant testimonials, and dissemination activities aimed at showcasing the project results to society. Technical papers will present the project outcomes, and they will be published in the most impactful international and European scientific conferences.

Demonstrations will showcase the datasets and toolkits at relevant showcase events. The project website will be continuously updated with storylines and insights, while final deliverables will be made available for download. Stakeholder-validated project outcomes will be assessed with direct feedback to achieve maximum impact and ensure that the project's most significant outputs are finalised during this period. A monitoring strategy will be realised with analytics and additional means used to measure KPI's.

Phase 4: Post funded period (M48+) During the post-funding phase, the Urban ReLeaf project team will continue to make all project results available for exploitation through appropriate exploitation plans and dissemination activities, as detailed in Deliverable 6.3 and updated in Deliverable 6.6. This phase will extend beyond the completion of the project and the publication of final results, aiming to advance the development of project outcomes beyond the funding period.

To ensure the maximum exploitation of results, the team will promptly respond to any requests from the European Commission and external entities. Moreover, the partners will seek recognition opportunities for results, including impact awards and competition entries.

The Urban ReLeaf website will be maintained for at least four years after the project's end to provide stakeholders with information about project accomplishments, resources, results, and contact persons. The team will plan for the potential for further development of project outcomes, such as scaling up the Urban ReLeaf pilot cities, expanding the project to new locations, or exploring new applications for the project's results. This will necessitate ongoing engagement with stakeholders and an active approach to identifying new opportunities for collaboration and funding.

Overall, the post-funding period will be a critical phase for the project, providing an opportunity to consolidate and disseminate project outcomes, promote uptake and sustainability, and explore new avenues for further development and impact.

1.3 Urban ReLeaf Audiences

The Urban ReLeaf consortium has recognized multiple groups who possess an interest in, will benefit from or will be impacted by the project. To effectively reach these audiences, various communication, and dissemination efforts, as well as networking and clustering activities, will be implemented. Our initial stakeholder mapping activities has defined broad categorisation

of stakeholder, target audiences and user groups. A table summarising the categorisations is provided below (Table 1). Following on a stakeholder mapping exercise further refines a targeted approach. As the project progresses and activities move through the different phases outlined in sections 1.2 so the ECD plan will target different stakeholder groups accordingly. This list is dynamic and will be refined with Pilot Cities to Month 12 and updated for each target group in Deliverable 6.3.

Table 1 Definition of Stakeholder categories with indicative target audiences and user groups

Stakeholder categories	Target Audiences and User Groups
Academic, Research and Scientific Community	Academic, Research and Scientific user groups, including Geography, environmental and data sciences, computing, climate science, earth observation, water, policy and law, engineers, social sciences, design, architecture, and urban planning.
City Stakeholders	City Councils, municipalities, communities, housing, planning, travel, leisure and parks authorities, public monitoring initiatives, culture, art and design professionals, and intermediary organizations, open data initiatives, authoritative data agencies, politicians, environmental, NGOs and CSO's
SME's and Industry	Climate technology, sensor manufacturers, software developers, External data agencies Data-driven innovation Civil engineers, planners, architects.
European and international networks, Government and public bodies, and policy makers	Encompassing innovation driven local, regional, national authorities, representatives & associations. National & International Public Administrations, Parliaments. EU standardisation bodies (ISO, CEN-CENELEC, ETSI, etc).
EU projects and networks working in similar domain	The participation of project partners in other relevant projects offers the opportunity to establish quick links among parties through joint actions e.g., Intelligent Cities Challenge (ICC)
The general public	A general audience not identified as core to the project, although they can have strong interest: citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups. Intermediary Organisations.
Diverse and Marginalised People	A core audience essential to the project's aims, including individuals and communities in urban locations of environmental concern and/or community experiencing multiple forms of deprivation.
Press & Media	Journalists for Local and National newspapers, Industry magazines, and technical, TV stations, local radio, press releases, social media. Influencers

1.3.1 Stakeholder mapping

Delivering a targeted ECD plan requires an understanding and prioritisation of different stakeholder needs and interests. A stakeholder mapping exercise identified a subset of target audiences and user groups (Table 1), using an ‘influence – interest’ grid positioned the audiences and groups outlined. The grid helps to identify which audiences and user groups are core, critical and require the most attention from the project. The focus for stakeholder mapping is phases 1 and 2 (Figure 2) and includes activities up to Month 28 to align with Deliverable 6.3. The mapping exercise has informed the outline of a stakeholder engagement matrix as part of the communications plan in section 2.

Figure 2: Outline of stakeholder Mapping with Urban ReLeaf Audience and User Groups Phases 1 and 2

Core stakeholders (pink segment) have a high influence / high interest, and a significant impact on the project. Their direct involvement is crucial for implementing Urban ReLeaf activities. They are central to the communications plan in phase 1 and 2. Stakeholders include NGOs, Civic Groups, Climate Action Groups, Climate Interest Groups, City Officials, Public Monitoring Initiatives, Marginalised People, City Council / Municipality Departments, Environmental Influencers, Local communities in target areas, Local press and media, Urban planning professionals, Architects, open data initiatives, authoritative data agencies.

Keep engaged (yellow segment) are stakeholder have high interest but low power. They will be kept informed and engaged so they stay aware of the project's progress without directly contributing to decision-making, therefore they are not as central to communications, including SME's and Industry, Creative Professionals, EU projects, Scientists, Academics and researchers, Active travel organisations, Leisure and park authorities,

Keep Interested (green segment): These stakeholders have high power but low interest. They can influence success but don't need to be involved in day-to-day operations. They will be communicated with to ensure their support including City Leaders, EPA's, policy-makers, Government agencies, Citizen science communities, journalists for national media, national and international networks. Technology sector / sensors,

Monitor (grey segment): These stakeholders have low power and low interest. They do not need to be targeted as with other stakeholders, but they should still be informed, including Civil engineers, general public, industry publications.

During phase 1 core stakeholders will be actively engaged in the project planning and decision-making process. They will provide input or refine aspects of the project research, goals, objectives, guidelines and strategies.

In phase 2 as the project progresses, some of the core stakeholders' roles shift, others move into the core frame, and others move out of the core focus.

We expand on the targets and core stakeholders in an outline communications plan and content objectives in section 2.2.

In order to maximize our reach, Urban ReLeaf's partners will utilise their networks of contacts at local, national, European, and international levels (Table 2). Certain networks have already provided letters of support to the consortium and received information about the project timeline and important dates immediately after its launch. Other networks will be engaged later to disseminate project results or for targeted communication.

Table 2 Networks of contacts at local, national, EU and international level

Local and national networks	Country
Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), Architecture Design Scotland (ADS), UNESCO Centre for Water, Policy and Law, Sustrans, Dundee Civic Trust	UK
Utrecht Nature and Environment Federation, Environmental Centre Utrecht, Measuring Utrecht Together, Association Utrecht Natuurlijk	NL
SynAthina, PANACEA Air Quality Network, Adopt-A-Tree Initiative, Sustainable City Network, Foundation Philodassiki Enossi Athinon, Atenistas, Elliniki Etairia. Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage	GR
Sustainable City Network, Local Gren Deal City Office, Climate Action Agency of Mannheim, Smart City GmbH, Municipality participation platform, Scientists for Future, Umweltforum Mannheim, Klimaschutzagentur Mannheim	DE
Movimento Azul Association, Landscape Architects Association, Resident Associations (Quinta da Carreira, Lombos Sul Association, etc.), Portuguese Institute for Nature conservation and forests	PT
Zero Waste Latvia, Community/Urban Garden associations (Sporta pils dārzi), Green Freedom, City of People, Green Riga Initiative, Augnīca	LV
European and International Networks	
UNESCO Cities of Design, European Citizen Science Association, ARUP, EPA Interest Group on Citizen Science, New European Bauhaus, EU Covenant of Mayors, EU Green City Accord, Citizen Science Global Partnership, SCS Marketplace, ICLEI	

In addition to these partner networks, the Pilot cities and Community of Practice (CoP) Working Group's will work with a wide range of stakeholders (e.g., public, and private actors, knowledge institutions, civic groups and/or non-government organisations), local communities and citizens that will be informed about the project objectives, and will take part in pilot workshops, assemblies and activities planned in 2024 and 2025. All these groups are

expected to greatly benefit from the project and become part of the Urban ReLeaf community. These will be mapped with the help of each pilot in the framework of WP4.

We will identify, build, and maintain a network for synergies with other communities, projects and institutions working on a similar domain. Among these, we have shortlisted those projects that we consider more relevant for Urban ReLeaf and T6.3 to reach out in the upcoming months to create synergies and maximize impact (Table 1). This list will be updated during the whole duration of the project.

Table 3 List of aligned projects and networks (T6.3)

Project Name and website	Objective
<p>CitiObs</p> <p>https://citiobs.eu/</p>	<p>CitiObs will consolidate and apply tools and practice-based knowledge for co-creating data, knowledge and local action via Citizen Observatories (COs): these tools will enhance existing and new citizen observatories to engage citizens and marginalised communities, add value to environmental observations in the urban context, increase and validate citizen observations of the urban environment as part of the existing in-situ Earth Observation systems, co-create inclusive local actions for sustainability and ensure that CO data contributes to research and policy development towards the objectives of the European Green Deal.</p>
<p>GREENGAGE</p> <p>https://www.greengage-project.eu/</p>	<p>GREENGAGE's vision is to promote innovative governance and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO), focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living supporting the delivery of carbon neutral neighbourhoods.</p>
<p>European Citizen Science</p>	<p>The overall objective of ECS is to widen and strengthen the European Citizen Science community through capacity building and awareness raising activities such as the creation of a European Citizen Science Academy and the establishment of a network of 28 ECS Ambassadors.</p>
<p>ECSA Working Group of Empowerment, Inclusiveness and Equity</p> <p>https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/working-groups/empowerment-inclusiveness-equity/</p>	<p>Working with organizers of projects in citizen science, community-based research, and other forms of participatory research to co-create resources and facilitate exchange on inclusiveness, equity, and empowerment in participatory research. The overall aim is that more people, from more diverse backgrounds, can participate in participatory research activities, shape them according to their wishes, and generate impacts that address their needs.</p>
<p>ARSINOE</p> <p>https://arsinoe-project.eu/</p>	<p>The ARSINOE project will shape the pathways to resilience by bringing together SIA (Systems Innovation Approach) and CIW (Climate Innovation Window) with the purpose to build an ecosystem for climate change adaptation solutions. Within the</p>

	ARSINOE ecosystem, pathways to solutions are co-created and co-designed by stakeholders, who can then select either existing CIW technologies, or technologies by new providers (or a combination) to form an innovation package.
<p>Socio-Bee</p> <p>https://socio-bee.eu/</p>	SOCIO-BEE proposes that community engagement and social innovation combined with Citizen Science (CS) through emerging technologies and playful interaction can bridge the gap between the capacity of communities to adopt more sustainable behaviours aligned with environmental policy objectives and between the citizen intentions and the real behaviour to act in favour of the environment (in this project, to reduce air pollution).
<p>Google Environmental Insights Explorer</p> <p>https://insights.sustainability.google/</p>	Environmental Insights Explorer (EIE) is a freely available data and insights tool that uses exclusive data sources and modelling capabilities to help cities and regions measure emissions sources, run analyses, and identify strategies to reduce emissions — creating a foundation for effective action.

1.4 The Communication Strategy

Having a well-defined and focused communications strategy is crucial to meet project goals effectively maximise time, resource and communicate, build awareness, engage stakeholders, increase impact, and create a lasting legacy. However, we are living in what is known as the ‘attention economy’ where information is abundant and attention is scarce, capturing and building the attention of audiences requires content that is engaging, relevant, and valuable. Therefore, we must also be strategic in the way we deliver our messages, using platforms and channels our stakeholders frequent. A communications funnel approach can help engage stakeholders by creating an emotional connection, highlighting unique aspects of our activities and results, creating a sense of urgency, and providing a clear call-to-action. As such, our goal is to create meaningful communications that prompt audiences to spread the word among their networks, following a content funnel approach that builds awareness, trust, a call to action and stimulates emotion, delight or joy (see 1.4.2).

1.4.1 Storytelling for Two

Our vision is to build audiences through the communication of important stories that get attention

The term "Storytelling for two" is a crucial part of our communication strategy. It emphasises the need for teams to focus on creating compelling narratives that will encourage people to share them with others. Storytelling involves designing communication rhythms, messages, and visual media that reinforce key messages and encourage participation. We will apply this

concept by tailoring messages, methods, and language to capture the audience's attention throughout the various phases and activities of Urban ReLeaf.

The Urban ReLeaf 'Storytelling for two' approach follows the six "W" questions: "Why? Who? What? When? Where? hoW?" to guide the development and framing.

- **Who?** Who are the target audiences and actors?
- **Why?** Why are we communicating, why do audiences need to know?
- **What?** What makes the issue urgent, what has happened or will happen? What solutions are we offering?
- **When?** Is this happening now, in the near term or further future? Is the communication a one-off, regular, and repeated, aligned with external event or opportunity?
- **Where?** Is this a highly local, national, European or global geographic context, aim to create a connection from local concerns to national or global issues.
- **HoW?** How does this relate to people in their everyday lives and more broadly to a bigger issue?
- **HoW?** How will we deliver the message through the most relevant medium or channel e.g., text, image, video, other is online, or physical?
- **What Impact?** What is the ideal outcome, is it effective and how will we follow up?

By following these points and following the 6W's and Storytelling for two approach we will position our research and innovation with messages that resonate with people's lives, and where appropriate, we will contextualise our results within a socio-economic and policy context to build strong audiences across the phases of Urban ReLeaf.

1.4.2 Key Drivers for Storytelling

A collaborative workshop session led by WP6 (UD) titled 'Urban ReLeaf Core Values and Branding' was delivered on 26 January 2023 at the Urban ReLeaf kick off meeting in Laxenburg, Austria. It explored strategies for the positioning and sharing of stories underpinned by the 6W's approach drawing from the partners personal experiences and perspectives. The following questions were explored after which the consortia shared responses (Figures 3, 4). The responses have been thematically analysed to inform the approach to building audiences through storytelling with Urban ReLeaf partners and are categorised below:

What are the **key drivers** for sharing a story?

- **Awareness and Knowledge Sharing:** Raise awareness, to share knowledge, discuss, brainstorm, and bounce ideas. new facts.
- **Emotional Connection:** Personal story you can relate to, emotions, get inspiration and take it to others, entertaining, fun
- **Impactful Ideas:** Sudden insight, gamechanger in thinking, call to action

Where are **people sharing stories**?

- **Open dialogue and debate** for example in public forums or platforms where people can openly express their views and engage in discussions and debates with others. Examples include community meetings and assemblies, public hearings, online forums, social media platforms, etc.
- **Verbal** includes spoken word communication. Examples include conversations between individuals, public presentations, debates, etc.
- **Word of Mouth** a subset of verbal but with an emphasis of trusted gatekeepers for information or stories that are shared among individuals through personal communication, most often in an informal setting. Examples include, personal recommendations, anecdotes, and catching up on local news etc.
- **Face to face:** any communication that takes place where individuals or groups are physically present with each other and interacting. Examples include at meetings, events, etc.

Which **digital platforms** are commonly used for storytelling?

- Professional networking: LinkedIn
- Photo and video sharing: Instagram
- General social networking: Facebook
- Microblogging and news sharing: Twitter
- Private and exclusive communication: Closed social network groups

Where are **the gaps or issues**?

- **Veracity** when the story being told is not completely accurate. This can happen when the narrator or characters are intentionally obscuring the truth, a story being told from different points of view, or perspectives, over-simplification, or when there is incomplete or incorrect information.

We also highlight the following gaps and issues to be aware of when using storytelling: inconsistency in the timeline, gaps, logic or reasoning; a lack of authenticity in the narrator or subjects' motivations, or actions, if the story fails to evoke meaning or an emotional response in the audience

Which ways might be most **successful for hard-to-reach communities**?

Successful approaches to engage hard-to-reach communities involve building trust, establishing direct relationships, using verbal, face to face and word of mouth approaches and creating safe spaces for dialogue, and using culturally appropriate communication channels.

Based on the provided responses from our partners, the most successful approaches to engage hard-to-reach communities can be categorized as follows:

- **Using trusted gatekeepers or intermediaries** involves working with trusted members of the community such as hairdressers or community groups to help build relationships with hard-to-reach groups.
- **Face-to-face and door-to-door engagement** involves going directly to the community to establish a relationship and build trust with members.

- **Dialogue sessions:** creating spaces for conversation and active listening, where community members can share their perspectives and ideas.
- **Filmmaking and story creation** involves working with communities to create stories and videos that reflect their experiences and perspectives.
- **Community insights and pop-up community and culture labs** involves creating temporary spaces in and for communities to come together, share ideas and learn from each other.
- **Using public spaces and local media:** using advertising and media outlets to reach out to hard-to-reach communities and communicate in plain language, while considering social variables, cultural differences and language barriers.

This provides an initial framing for our strategy, our website, social media channels and other digital communications which needs to reach intermediary and trusted representatives who will then subsequently engage our target communities using face to face and verbal approaches.

EXERCISE 1

Step 1 The 'W's

5mins

- Think of the 'Story' you shared
1. What was the 'Story' and asset
e.g. film, visualisation, report
 2. Who did you share it with
 3. Where or how did you share it
 4. Why did you share it?

When your group had completed one story per person move on to Step 2

Step 2 Clustering

7mins

Figure 3 Storytelling workshop session, applying the '6W's

Figure 4 Storytelling workshop session, insights, key drivers and ways of sharing to support participation

1.4.3 Project values and communications

Our fundamental Ethics and Values are defined in Article 14 of the Grant Agreement outlines the basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities) for responsible research and innovation (RRI).

In addition to the commitments outlined above, our goal is to ensure consistency in our messaging by establishing shared values that guide the tone of our content. In line with this objective, WP6 has led the development of specific values for Urban ReLeaf. These values will help us to create a compelling and memorable communication strategy that resonates with our target audience through storytelling.

The approach and workshop sessions outlined in section 1.4.1 Storytelling for two and 1.4.2 Key Drivers was followed by a workshop session exploring the ‘core values’ that underpin our project for the delivery of a citizen observatory. We describe the session below:

Participants were divided into four groups, they were asked to brainstorm values that the associated with Urban ReLeaf, following this they voted in their groups on their top 4 values

(Figure 5). The words that received the most votes from partners were: Inspiring, Evidence-Based, Just and Inclusive with second tier words being Transparent, Empowering, Well-being and Joyous/Fun. Further analysis of all responses revealed participants attributed values that can helpfully guide our approach to engaging and working with people and to our project goals regarding science and impact. We have arranged these thematically:

Inspiring:	Inspiration, Inspirational, Joyous, Empowering
Evidence-Based:	Transparent, Transparency, Simplicity, Reliable
Impactful:	Transformative
Just:	Collaborative, Inclusiveness, Accessible, Simplicity, Well-being

We categorised the themes that attracted the most votes and added contributions to the top 4 voted values from each group to expand the theme. Some values could fit into multiple themes, some may also be exchanged with another in the category to facilitate translation, simplification or ease of understanding. Decision-making on the final values and descriptions will be revisited and finalised in a session with the consortium.

1.4.4 Inclusive Engagement and Green Guidelines

Urban ReLeaf will apply an inclusive communication and engagement strategy amongst all communication materials as well as engagement aspects of the pilots' activities. This strategy will ensure equal accessibility to as many people as possible, regardless of race, age, ethnicity, and gender to avoid the common social exclusion phenomenon present in many CS projects. Specific attention will be paid to the inclusion of women, and vulnerable or marginalised groups who are disproportionately impacted by environmental hazards.

With the set-up of this inclusive communication and engagement strategy, we aim to:

- Include diverse audiences in the pilots' activities of Urban ReLeaf. We aim for a target of a 50% minimum share of female participants, and 30% marginalized and vulnerable groups (e.g., elderly, or young people who are vulnerable to heat induced stress).
 - Gender KPI: The aim is to reach a good gender balance between females and males and reaching a target share of 50% female participants. Women are often underrepresented in science activities, and also specifically in citizen science³. The intention is not to obtain an overrepresentation of females in the project, i.e. a disproportionately high presences of a certain group, but rather an inclusive, and diverse audience that reflects the broader population.
- Raise awareness about inclusiveness and ethical values amongst all project partners and participants of Urban ReLeaf,
- Offer guidance and training to the project partners related to inclusive communication, recruitment, and engagement processes.

The implementation of this inclusive engagement and communication strategy will include the following activities:

- An **inclusive communication policy** that presents Urban ReLeaf's core vision about diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), with specific guidelines we like to adhere to, as well as a mechanism for reporting inappropriate conduct. Participants of the Urban ReLeaf project are able co-write this statement, and their feedback collected during the participatory workshops of WP2.T2.2 will be considered. This policy will be published on the project's website by M8.
- An **inclusive checklist** for partners to apply to all communications and events as part of the communication pack (delivered M8). This will include guidance on inclusive language and visuals, and guidance on locations, facilities, event information and appropriate communication channels. Amongst others, this checklist will include tips for plain and simple language, and references to readability tools. All external communications materials should be validated with the help of this checklist. In case of any doubts, the EDI-manager of Urban ReLeaf can advise the partners on how to make the communication materials more inclusive.

³ Paleco, C., García Peter, S., Salas Seoane, N., Kaufmann, J., Argyri, P., Vohland, K., ... & Wagenknecht, K. (2021). Inclusiveness and diversity in citizen science. *The science of citizen science*, 261, 261-282.

- **Four internal DEI trainings** will be organised during the project and are applicable and beneficial to all partners to pay extra attention to inclusion and ethical guidelines. Potential topics are: “How to organize an inclusive event”, “Inclusive communication in citizen science: simple and plain language”, “Recruitment strategies for reaching underrepresented groups in science”, etc. In total, four trainings will be organised by VUB and invited external speakers (e.g., from the advisory board, and others). Each training will last for approximately 1h30min, including a Q&A-session.
- **All pilot cities attain a four-step recruitment process to ensure a diverse audience.** The first step is to specify key performance indicators for inclusive engagement (see indicators above). Next, a general call is launched with an open invitation to join the project’s activities, e.g., via social media, the press, etc. The second step defines specific inclusion criteria (socio-economic and socio-demographic characteristics) relevant to the pilots’ scope that need to be attained. If well justified and considered ethically, demographic characteristics will be collected from the participants through a survey form. The last step is a targeted approach, focusing on the missing profiles and underrepresented groups, e.g., through personal invitations and local partnerships with trusted intermediaries such as CBOs. This approach is thus used for all target audiences to be recruited in the pilot activities in order to ensure that their audiences are inclusive and diverse.
- **A monitoring plan for inclusive engagement:** Through the usage of a monitoring template, demographic analyses of participant profiles will be regularly performed where possible and ethically justified. This will occur at least once a year and at specific milestones in the project.

This process is overseen by Urban ReLeaf Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Manager Ms. Carina Veeckman (VUB).

Green Guidelines We will establish the project urban green communication policy to ensure that all communication materials and activities are designed to reduce the impact on the environment. These project values will be published in a project statement on the website and best practice and lessons learned in applying it will be shared as part of deliverables from T6.2. We will

- Create stakeholder messages that adhere to our strategy, minimising unnecessary ‘push’ communications.
- Use audience appropriate digital communication channels.
- Minimise the use of paper and transportation-related emissions.
- Where print materials are necessary, we will adhere to environmentally conscious design principals whilst meeting accessible guidelines.
 - Use recycled paper and print on both sides.

- Reduce the font size and margins optimise text onto each page.
- Procure environmentally friendly materials for workshops, such as recycled pens and paper.

Urban ReLeaf also aims at minimising project and partner travel, conducting meetings, conferences and public engagement online where practical, procuring green travel options, communicating and encouraging participants to adopt green travel options when attending project activities and events in person.

Our green guidelines project statement will be published on the project website. This will ensure project partners and stakeholders are aware of our green communication policy and understand the importance of reducing the impact on the environment.

2 Part 2: Communication Plan and Dissemination Tools

The objectives of the communication activities for Urban ReLeaf will facilitate effective communication between existing networks and to a wide audience. A communication dashboard, tools and channels will be used to target different groups to reach our core audiences as well as widen opportunity for participation. These communication activities will exploit the multiplication effect possible by having partners who bring their networks from existing relevant projects and existing city partner networks.

2.1 Communication Plan

The initial stakeholder mapping exercise (section 1.3.1) segmented core stakeholder groups according to the previously identified project phases. We expand this exercise to include an outline of the communication action and an outline of our objectives for content creation. The plan will be rapidly iterated to Month 9 as pilot cities define their focus and core stakeholders and our communications strategy is updated accordingly. The Stakeholder engagement matrix (Table 1) shows priority audiences and user groups from our initial stakeholder mapping (Table 1). It aligns to phases 1 and 2, with our communications strategy and objectives for content creation. This work aligns to our chosen dissemination tools in section 2.3.

Table 4 Stakeholder Engagement Matrix showing audience categories, phase with objectives for content creation

Audience or User Group	Phase	Communication Action	Objectives for Content Creation
City Pilot Intermediary Organisations	1	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness and connect with target audiences to support participation and co-creation activities Provide targeted translation of content and resources for local languages Tell accessible stories that encourage citizens to participate in Pilot City campaign activities Develop a city-based communication strategy that reaches the organisations and builds relationships.
City Officials	1	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate the concept and benefits of Urban ReLeaf for the EU to meet Green Deal goals. Communicate the value of citizen-powered data ecosystems Raise awareness about the role of citizen science in promoting green transitions Disseminate project and outcomes to the target groups through the phases of the project
Environmental NGOs	1, 2	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness about the importance of Urban ReLeaf and its impact on lives, local community and environment.

			Demonstrate the concept and benefits of Urban ReLeaf for the EU to meet Green Deal goals.
Local Community Groups / Civic Groups	1, 2	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<p>Develop a city-based communication strategy that reaches the organisations and builds relationships.</p> <p>Raise awareness about the importance of Urban ReLeaf and its impact on lives, local community and environment.</p> <p>Inform and encourage the peoples about opportunities to join Urban ReLeaf</p> <p>Provide targeted translation of content and resources for local languages</p>
Other Monitoring Initiatives	1	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<p>Communicate the value of citizen-powered data ecosystems</p> <p>Highlight upcoming Urban ReLeaf data services</p>
Environmental Influencers, Climate Action Groups	1,2	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<p>Inform and encourage the peoples about opportunities to join Urban ReLeaf</p> <p>Raise awareness about the project outputs, results, and innovation among the target audience.</p> <p>Foster relationships and partnerships to enhance collaboration and support for the project.</p>
Diverse / Marginalised People	1	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	<p>Tell accessible stories that encourage citizens to participate in Pilot City campaign activities</p> <p>Inform and encourage the peoples about opportunities to join Urban ReLeaf</p> <p>Encourage participation by providing resources and support to make it easy for them to do so.</p>
Local and Targeted Press And Media	1, 2	Keep Informed, Collaborate	<p>Increase engagement with the through press releases, targeted social media etc</p> <p>Promote Urban ReLeaf to the press and media to maximize impact</p> <p>Support citizen science milestones and successes through press releases and feature</p> <p>Generate news and events related to green transitions and the creation of new value from citizen science</p> <p>Reach out to scientific and environmental press & media to share relevant news and events</p> <p>Disseminate project and outcomes to the target groups through the phases of the project</p>
Architects Urban Planning	2	Consult, Collaborate	Exchange of knowledge, technologies, and methodologies among the target audience.

Professionals			Inform and encourage the peoples about opportunities to join Urban ReLeaf Raise awareness about the upcoming project outputs, results, and innovation among the target audience.
EPAs	2	Consult, Collaborate	Create messaging that adds value to national EPA's,NGOs and public monitoring initiatives Promote joint working to reach key target audiences e.g., Policy, Scientific Disseminate project and outcomes to the target groups through the phases of the project
Creative Professionals	2	Consult, Collaborate	Create compelling content (e.g., videos, infographics, interviews) that can be easily shared
Open Data Initiatives	2	Keep Informed, Consult	Facilitate the reuse of data generated by the project among the target audience Exchange of knowledge, technologies, and methodologies among the target audience.
Authoritative Data Agencies	2	Keep Informed, Consult, Collaborate	Facilitate the reuse of data generated by the project among the target audience Exchange of knowledge, technologies, and methodologies among the target audience. Raise awareness about the upcoming project outputs, results, and innovation among the target audience. Disseminate project and outcomes to the target groups through the phases of the project

2.2 Visual Identity

The project branding will communicate the identity, values and vision of Urban ReLeaf and will help partners share information about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. The project branding encompasses a dynamic and still project logo, visual identity, written identity including tagline and key messages and templates for Word and PowerPoint documents. A brand book will outline the application of the visual identity in both online and offline formats.

The workshop sessions described in 1.4.2 and 1.4.3 with all partners established a shortlist of project values to underpin the development of the project identity. Part of the same workshop explored brand preferences, where the full consortium was asked to provide examples of brands and websites whose identify, design and messaging, resonated with them, giving reasons why (Figure 6). Together these materials informed a professional design brief to be launched as part of D6.2 (M6).

What branding inspires us? 20mins

EXERCISE 4

The grid contains 48 cards, each representing a branding inspiration. Key examples include:

- SCORE EU:** Logo and colour palette mirrors the rhythm of the sea.
- Nudi:** This is the key idea. Note: Love the illustration as they are appealing to both kids and adults.
- Shift Design:** This is the key idea. Note: Design thinking for collective impact: built.
- Nature Decks:** This is the key idea. Note: Nature Deck is great connecting nature to our outdoor spaces.
- Felco:** Note: Our logo is a simple illustration of a pair of scissors, which is a great metaphor for the brand's mission.
- Naturvation:** Note: The database with inspiring projects from across the world. Love the layout of long sections. The way content is laid out.
- Patagonia:** Note: Love the colours, really striking. Organic, fair trade and sustainable business model. Great graphics and typography. My favourite place I have visited. I love Patagonia.
- Patagonia (another card):** Note: I like how the design brings a sense of place and nature into the brand.
- Patagonia (third card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (fourth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (fifth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (sixth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (seventh card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (eighth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (ninth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (tenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (eleventh card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twelfth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirteenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (fourteenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (fifteenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (sixteenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (seventeenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (eighteenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (nineteenth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twentieth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-first card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-second card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-third card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-fourth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-fifth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-sixth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-seventh card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-eighth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (twenty-ninth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirtieth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-first card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-second card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-third card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-fourth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-fifth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-sixth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-seventh card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-eighth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (thirty-ninth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (fortieth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-first card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-second card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-third card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-fourth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-fifth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-sixth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-seventh card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-eighth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (forty-ninth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.
- Patagonia (fiftieth card):** Note: I like the platform because it has a focus on nature and organic and sustainable. Love the way it's laid out. I love the graphics.

Figure 6 Documentation of co-design workshop session 'Branding that Inspires Us'

2.3 'In person' Tools

The following section outlines the tools and measures to reach target stakeholders described in sections 1 and followed up in the stakeholder engagement matrix. It also outlines and expands on those tools that support activities in person (Table 5).

Table 4 Summary of key engagement, communication tools and dissemination to support in person activity

Offline Tools and Activities	Description	Channel	Target Stakeholder
Communication materials	<p>A project communication package (M6) containing the main elements of the project will be available as: a presentation, poster, banner, and document (one-page project description, objectives, impacts) including logo, visual identity materials and templates.</p> <p>- 1 flyer (M6), 1 final brochure (Mn), 1 timeline infographic (M12).</p> <p>Representation and dissemination of results, outputs, outcomes and impact will be communicated with features via the website and blog.</p> <p>A city communication package (M8) with guidelines, checklists, exemplars and templates. 3 training sessions will be provided to collaboratively devise bespoke storylines for each city.</p>	Printed and digital assets and guidance to support in person events, measures and activities. Distributed through project SharePoint, bespoke plans designed in collaboration	All
Press and Media Communications	Traditional media incl. press releases, radio, local and national newspapers, and TV	A press pack with project assets provided in print and digitally	Press and Media contacts, City Stakeholders, General Public, All
Engagement Measures, Events and Activities	Urban ReLeaf has a range of diverse measures, events and activities that are expanded upon below (see 2.1.2) to maximise its reach in person to disseminate project activities and results as well as increase exploitation by harnessing the networking capacity of the community.	In person, one to one, in groups, project activities and external events	All
Scientific Publications (Journal Papers, Presentations, Posters, workshops)	Our scientific publications will widely disseminate the project outcomes and results.	Conferences, events including policy and engagement	GEO, EEA, EPA Interest Group on Citizen Science network. Science, industry, design, and social science journals

2.3.1 Communication materials

The Consortium is committed to raising awareness and generating stakeholder and media interest in the project by producing and publishing articles in English and 5 other languages. The goal is to inform and engage a wide range of audiences and encourage local and national press, magazines and other media outlets to feature articles on the project's concept, progress, and results. The following communication materials will be prepared and distributed to the project partners to ensure effective communication and increase public awareness of the project.

- **Communications Resources (M6 – M48)** available on the project SharePoint. This living resource will be added to as the project matures, it will focus on project level communication, including : branding guidelines, identity assets, stage 1 stakeholder mapping, a timeline with highlight campaigns, key messages, visual library (photographs, infographics and media), social media guidance (tone, hashtags and handles) and guidance on monitoring for personal and partner media accounts. Branded templates including presentations, poster and related materials.
- **Communication Pack (M8)** will be created to support the communication and dissemination efforts of partners, with a specific focus on Pilot Cities. This pack will provide guidance and training for customised communication plans at the local level. It will include an overview of the project, key messages, key audiences and a template for creating compelling storylines, as well as press release examples and the core social media strategy and channels. The pack will also feature guidelines for capturing high-quality media and images (including ALT text requirements) and accreditation, as well as information on monitoring and evaluation. Additionally, it will provide quick access to project-level assets such as flyers, banners, logos, presentation slides, webinar backdrops, and videos.
- **Communications Training for Pilot City Strategies (M8 – 10)** WP6 will provide a minimum of 3 city level workshops to support the bespoke co-design of communication strategies using the communications pack and DEI checklist. A presentation will be followed by a collaborative online session to provide hands-on experience of using the communication pack and tools. City specific follow-on meetings will support partners to develop strategies and key messaging bespoke to their focus of activities. Participants will include Urban ReLeaf city partners, relevant partner communications experts, citizen science leads, another persona as required
- **Storylines and Case studies (M15 – 20)** Workshop sessions will be provided as required to develop storylines and case studies from City Pilot activities. Identifying case studies and success stories will inspire and motivate the target audience, provide content for the Urban ReLeaf Blog and Newsletter, and will also inform the narrative structure of the Urban ReLeaf video and potential participant testimonials.

Furthermore, WP6 will provide guidance on the following:

- Media outreach to gain exposure for pilot activities at local level. This will include advice on developing local media lists (retained by partners due to GDPR), writing press releases as outlined previously, and pitching stories through their organisations to journalists.

2.3.2 Press and Media Communications (M8 – 48)

We will develop press and communications around key messages adhering to our storytelling strategy and we will cover key milestones agreed collaboratively by project partners. The aim is to generate media coverage in partner countries and EU-wide, as well as feeding various blogs (e.g., Bauhaus Initiative, ECSA, IIASA Nexus blog, ICLEI blogs). Dissemination through EU channels will also be pursued, e.g., the Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine or Futuris Magazine.

- **Urban ReLeaf Press pack (M8)** will build on the above and encompass press releases, project background and information, images and multimedia, contact information, statistics and data, and important a range of testimonials or quotes from partners and stakeholders. It will contain high quality images and text for ready use by journalists.
- **Media Contacts (M8 – M48)** We are preparing of a Media Contacts dashboard of outlets and journalists that cover the core Urban ReLeaf topic area, with specific lists for each Pilot City. Our strategy is to prepare press and media materials, and to leverage the appropriate lead partner press and media offices. We will target outlets e.g., publications, websites, TV stations or radio programs, and journalists who have covered similar stories in the past, taking this approach at a local level can subsequently lead to follow on interest and coverage at national coverage. The media list is organised by outlet, journalist, and contact information with general notes about coverage and interests and will be kept updated through the phase of delivery.
- **Pitching Story Ideas (M10 – M48)** Getting press attention frequently involves building relationships with key press and media outlets with a follow-on pitch for the story, this requires research, planning, and persistence. One approach is to prepare a press release or media advisory to outline the details of the story, including the key message, the hook and the angle. A press release may be followed by a pitch to a target journalist, editor, producer or outlet. The pitch should be brief and to the point, and it might include references to previous articles the journalist has written or highlight points on how the story relates to their audience or outlet. The University of Dundee issued a joint press release in related to the Dundee pilot on 6 March 2023, followed by a pitch as ⁴

⁴ <https://www.dundee.ac.uk/stories/help-drive-green-urban-futures-across-europe>

If articles are not authored by the partners, a copy of the article and press release, along with all necessary information, should be sent to the communications lead to ensure that all relevant information is shared and disseminated effectively.

Press clippings related to the project will be routinely updated on the Urban ReLeaf website. This will provide a comprehensive repository of all media coverage related to the project, making it easier for interested parties to access information and stay up to date with the latest developments.

2.3.3 Engagement Measures and Events

Figure 7 Urban ReLeaf timeline key engagement measures and events

Urban ReLeaf will hold a series of dedicated events, workshops, and activities during the project lifetime for active and face-to-face dissemination and exploitation. A detailed timeline for these events with prior notice periods for preparation will be developed in collaboration with partners. The events and the timeline outlined in Figure 7. encompass the following activities:

- Urban ReLeaf Pilot co-design and implementation with city led stakeholder workshops
- Pop-up Community and Culture Labs
- Insights Workshops
- Design for Business Sprints
- Accelerator Programme
- Communities of Practice and Working Groups
- GEOSS demonstrators
- Conference Participation

Urban ReLeaf Pilot Co-design and Campaigns (co-design M1 – 12, campaign implementation M13 – 36+)

To disseminate and communicate the main results of the observation and measurement campaigns in an accessible, visually appealing way, e.g., in the form of online maps and result factsheets

- **Pop-up Community and Culture Labs (M13– 36)**
 In the second year of the project Local “Community and Culture Pop-up Labs” will invite a range of stakeholders bespoke to each Pilot City focus to engage citizens in the urban greening discourse, raise awareness and spur interest in environmental monitoring. In collaboration with local artists and citizen associations, artistic and design-based innovation activities will be offered. Bespoke labs will be aligned with specific city events. Sensor data and visualisations will feed into future scenario building sessions and rapid prototyping games to co-create community-oriented greening solutions. The generated outputs will be synthesized into D2.3 and will feature as stories on the Urban ReLeaf website. We will target engagement to increase the diversity of participants, including from identified marginalized and vulnerable groups.
 Stakeholders: city stakeholders, policy makers, general public and press / media
- **Insights Workshops (M34 – 45)**
 In the second half of the project, Insights Workshops in each city will discuss campaign results and jointly elaborate solutions and policy options. Reflection on integrated datasets, citizen-generated data and experience stories from Urban ReLeaf campaigns. Derived insights and lessons learned will be shared with participants and contribute to the Urban ReLeaf Toolkit and Roadmap Insight workshops will also enable reflective dialogues of results and consolidate joint lessons learned. Insights Workshops will close the co-creation circle with a reflective perspective and enable discussion across different stakeholder groups.
 Stakeholders: citizens, scientists, policy makers, civic groups, urban planning and other stakeholders
- **Accelerator Programme (M34 – 48)**
 Concrete steps will be taken from year 2 onwards to investigate potential exploitation of project results and amplification of the Urban ReLeaf experience post-project. We will invite interested cities to join the Accelerator Programme aimed at identifying opportunities and barriers to the further up-take and implementation of the Urban ReLeaf experience.
 Stakeholders: 10 additional cities and their relevant stakeholders.
- **Conference Participation (M1 – 48)** Urban ReLeaf partners will promote the project at workshops, through conference presentations, via side events of scientific meetings, scientific publications and other public appearances organized in collaboration with GEO, EEA, ECSA and the EPA Interest Group on Citizen Science network.
 Stakeholders: academics and researchers, scientists, EPA’s, related research organisations and institutes
- **Urban ReLeaf Community of Practice (M10 – 48+) builds** on the knowledge and networks established by partners in the consortium (IIASA, ICCS, UD) to establish Communities of Practice (CoPs) in order to consolidate and extend the network for Urban ReLeaf. CoPs aim to enhance visibility, strengthen mutual learning, and promote inclusive urban green transitions beyond the consortium. They will maximise its reach to disseminate project activities and results as well as increase

exploitation by harnessing the networking capacity of the community. CoP members will be recruited through two open calls via the website, social media channels, online newsletter and through direct mail to our networks to recruit participants (M12, M24), targeting cities, relevant stakeholders, academics, civil society organisations and related communities. We will also target our existing links to working groups via WeObserve and through our associations such as ECSA, GEO and our Advisory Board

Three initial Working Groups (WG) for the CoPs have been selected:

- **WG 1: Triggering innovation in public authorities with citizen-powered science** (Lead: ICLEI) Key Stakeholders: Municipalities, Citizen associations, CSOs, business community
- **WG 2: Coupling citizen science and EO for European Green Deal & SDG 11 monitoring** (Lead: IIASA) Key Stakeholders: Municipalities, Authoritative data agencies, GEO, EuroGEO, Copernicus,
- **WG 3: Urban design foresight for NBS and BGI scenario planning** (Lead: UD) Key Stakeholders: Municipalities, Urban Planners, Architects, EPAs

Furthermore, the Community of Practice (WP5) will maximise the project reach to disseminate project activities and results via the website and through social media channels as well as increase exploitation by harnessing the networking capacity of the community. Details of the CoP programme, terms of reference and guidelines will be agreed by WP5.

2.3.4 Scientific Publications and Outputs

The Urban ReLeaf project aims to promote its research and findings to a wide audience through various channels outlined in 2.2. One of the key strategies for disseminating the project's publications involves partnering with GEO, EEA, EPA Interest Group on Citizen Science network, and organizing workshops, scientific meetings, and conference presentations. The project consortium will leverage these opportunities to showcase their work and raise awareness about their findings to stakeholders through communications channels outlined including in articles for Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine. Publication of these outputs will be disseminated via the website, relevant social media channels and via the newsletter.

The consortium is committed to publishing via high impact journals. To ensure that the project's publications are accessible to as many people as possible, the consortium will attribute a DOI to all outputs and encourage partners to actively update their ORCID profiles to enable findability. The project will use Green Open Access to make their publications available through various repositories, such as Open AIRE. However, the consortium also recognises the importance of Gold Open Access and will encourage partners to publish via this route. The project also adheres to FAIR principles, which stand for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. This is a set of guidelines for scientific data management and publishing developed to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability

of scientific data. Implementing these will help promote transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration within and beyond the scientific community to key stakeholders in Urban ReLeaf.

In addition to publications, the Urban ReLeaf project will also produce other open science outputs, including the Urban ReLeaf Toolkit and Roadmap (WP5), wearable sensors for temperature and humidity, Tree mapping applications, Tree registry datasets, Bioclimatic comfort monitoring application, Temp and humidity datasets, High-res green elements layers for Urban Atlas products, Online data visualisations, Protocols and citizen observation guidelines, Governance models, Impact evaluation datasets, results, and impact briefs. These resources will be available under the appropriate license, as a default we will use a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license. All the above outputs will be accessible and or linked to through the Urban ReLeaf website, as well as available on the permanent Urban ReLeaf community on Zenodo, and the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Where relevant the project will provide open-source apps e.g., tree mapping application and monitoring software, which will be shared via GitHub and integrated into the Urban ReLeaf Zenodo community and linked to the project website.

By making all these resources open and accessible, the Urban ReLeaf project aims to maximize the impact of its research and contribute to the wider scientific community.

2.4 Online Tools

Online tools and platforms have become an essential and core feature for effective research and innovation communication and dissemination. The following tools have been selected on the basis of their ability to efficiently communicate to a range of stakeholders through different phases of delivery. They include a project website, social networks/online platforms, audiovisual materials, and online research dissemination platforms. Through these tools, Urban ReLeaf will engage with a wide range of stakeholders and effectively communicate project activities, findings, and outcomes. Moreover, these tools allow for rapid and widespread dissemination of project results, which will significantly enhance the impact of the research and innovation efforts. An overview of the tools can be seen in Table 6 with a detailed description below.

Table 5 Key online engagement, communication tools and dissemination activity

Online Tools and Activities	Description	Channel	Target Stakeholder
Project Website	The project website will contain information targeted to the general public and stakeholders (Urban ReLeaf vision and objectives, WPs, Partners, City Pilots, Technology, Events). It will foreground a storytelling 'magazine' approach to content. Specific hashtags will curate information targeted towards the different types of stakeholders including linked to the project (Cities, Data, Events, Newsletter, People, Press, Publications, Toolkit)	Web	All

Social Networks / Online Platforms	<p>All project partners' will re-share content to direct their audience to Urban ReLeaf channels and website.</p> <p>In doing so, the consortium benefits from partners' established audiences, while building a strong brand that can live beyond the 4-year project and thus have an extended impact on urban green transitions, urban transformation.</p> <p>By adding relevant hashtags i.e., as #Horizon Europe #NBS #citizenscience project reach will be further amplified.</p>	<p>LinkedIn and Twitter</p> <p>Facebook and Instagram</p> <p>Personal and institutional social media accounts</p>	<p>professional, academic, technology stakeholders,</p> <p>partner accounts, existing local community groups, the general public.</p>
Audio Visual Materials	<p>1 project film for awareness raising and promotion to engage pilot cities and present the project in its early stages and 1 project film that focuses on testimonials, result and impact</p> <p>12 short videos and vox pops.</p> <p>Animated project identified and related assets to communicate the project concept, values and impact</p>	<p>Project Website, TV segments, Audio-visual channels incl YouTube</p> <p>Wide online dissemination</p>	<p>All Participants in a film</p> <p>Press and Media</p>
Online Research Dissemination Platforms	<p>Publications will be given a DOI and uploaded to the. Academic partners will update publications to their personal ORCID to ensure search and citation opportunities are maximised.</p>		<p>Zenodo and Institutional repository. EU platforms</p>

2.4.1 Project Website

The project website, currently under construction, is located at <https://urbanreleaf.eu>, is an essential tool for Urban ReLeaf to increase its visibility and communicate project activities, deliverables, and outcomes to a wide audience. Along with social media, the website is key to the engagement, communication and dissemination plan. Specifically, the website will give stakeholders the opportunity to sign up to various news and activities e.g., newsletter, community of practice working groups. It will also disseminate project results. The website provides comprehensive information on the project, including its concept and objectives, workplan, partners, activities, research and innovation, information on pilot cities, news, publications and deliverables. It also features Urban ReLeaf's Inclusivity Statement and Green Guidelines. We plan to update the website through its phases with content targeted towards different types of stakeholders involved in the project such as feature blog articles, training materials, scientific papers, and toolkits.

In addition to the project website, both IIASA and the University of Dundee have created a one-page project page (Figure 8) on their institutional websites, which were published online in January 2023. These pages provide information about the project's aims, partners, funding references, and contacts for stakeholders. This early web presence has assisted with our initial communications with press and media.

Figure 8 From left to right IIASA Urban ReLeaf Project website, University of Dundee Urban ReLeaf Project website

A fully functional website is launched in Month 6 (D6.2, UD), Representative wireframes of a selection of project pages, including the homepage, project information, pilot cities overview, and pilot city, are shown in Figure 8 as an example.

2.4.2 Social Networks and Online Platforms

The project aims to broaden its impact and reach a diverse audience through the utilisation of several social media platforms, which are follow a ‘hub’ and ‘spoke’ model

Urban ReLeaf core ‘hub’ channels are defined as core project channels developed specifically for the project and which communicate and share project specific activities. Urban ReLeaf ‘spoke’ channels comprise existing partner social media channels that have established audiences and whose communications represent a broad spectrum of communications; they will communicate key messages concerning Urban ReLeaf Pilot activity. Additional ‘spoke’ local channels may be created to enable Pilot City communications in line with our requirements, these will determine during pilot city workshops.

A carefully crafted social media strategy will be employed to align our Hub and Spoke communications with our chosen stakeholder audiences. Social media is an ideal channel for disseminating information efficiently, and it offers a targeted approach to reach different audiences. We are currently undertaking the following steps which will develop the strategy in full, it includes considerations for both hub and spoke communications:

Figure 9 Urban ReLeaf website wireframes, from left to right, Homepage, Project Information, Pilot Cities, City Focus

1. **Create Urban ReLeaf ‘hub’ accounts** Our social media accounts are the primary means by which all communication is disseminated i.e., project activities, events, messages, outputs, and results.
2. **Identify and engage City Partner Channels and Accounts:** Ensure that they align with the project's goals and objectives. We will consider the most appropriate social media channels already in use by each city partner and assess which will be most effective to engage local audiences to communicate pilot specific activities.
3. **Develop Content Plan and Calendar** using the communications resources, pack and strategies outlined in this deliverable and in training workshops with partners. Including key messages, outputs, events, and results to be communicated through the hub and spoke channels.
4. **Support and amplify City Partners:** (see Communications pack 2.1.2) we will Share and amplify partners' content through the hub channels, to provide broader reach and visibility to their local communities, as well as to showcase the diversity of the project's impact across different contexts.
5. **Monitor with an Evaluation plan:** to ascertain the effectiveness of the core and city channels' communication strategies, using metrics outlines in section 3 and including engagement rates, reach, and impressions, to promote improvement and alignment with the project's goals.

Urban ReLeaf Core Channels

It should be noted that building a following on each platform requires significant effort. To overcome this challenge, we will define the specific objectives and purposes of each platform in the tables below. By leveraging the strengths of each platform, we can maximize our online presence and enhance the visibility of our project. The following online channels will be created and launched in Month 6 as part of Deliverable 6.2:

- Facebook
- Instagram
- LinkedIn
- Twitter
- YouTube

Urban ReLeaf will apply both the Storytelling for two approach and application of the “6 W’s” to inform the messaging and structure of posts, post frequency, official hashtags, partners/researchers’ accounts handle, overview of main topics to align with project and pilot city activities and campaigns. An outline of the planned communication channels can be found in the tables 7-11 below:

Table 6 Facebook channel with rationale for use

Facebook	@releafcities
Why use it?	Facebook effectively communicates with the general public in a straightforward manner and provides targeted sponsored campaign tools. It can also fulfil the need for "closed groups," as identified in the WP6 workshop during the kick-off meeting.
Media	Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness and communicate about the project, highlight opportunities, activities and calls to action, and showcase project results in an informal, highly accessible way to engage. • Share and amplify project communications from pilot cities, and those of project partners and individual team members.
Target Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established community groups taking part or acting as trusted gatekeepers for the project often have an established Facebook presence. particularly for mature members of the community. • City Stakeholders, Project Team Individuals
Content Structure	Facebook’s approach aligns with Urban ReLeaf Storytelling for two being ‘easily shareable’ and immediately understandable. It may lead to more in-depth content or other follow up actions taken by audiences. It focuses on engaging visual material/infographics, pictures, quotes, and storytelling.

Table 7 Instagram channel with rationale for use

Instagram	@releafcities
Why use it?	Instagram is relevant to young audiences, creative professionals, SMEs, and local activities. It’s useful for sharing visual updates, stories about local events, and upcoming activities as calls to action.
Media	Text description together with an images or videos.

	It is possible to tag other accounts (people, products, and organisations) and to use content or location specific hashtags to make posts more discoverable. There are features, such as Reels (videos), photos or carousels (mix of narrative based video and images) that gives the possibility of posting specific narrative-based content.
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness and communicate about the project to a younger audience • To engage the wider public activities e.g., pop-up community labs; to expand city pilot networks involvement. • To showcase project update and results in an informal and narrative based way. • To share visually engaging material
Target Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainly younger audiences • Designers and artists engaged with city pilot Pop-up and Culture Labs • City Pilots to share visually compelling content in their own voice
Content Structure	<p>Posts include pictures, graphic elements and quotes, and descriptions with visual material.</p> <p>Relevant partners or individual team members tagged; geotags are used when relevant.</p> <p>Official Hashtags are used, with additional hashtags as appropriate.</p> <p>Carousels may be used for storytelling in City Pilots. Reshares of other posts are used when relevant.</p>

Table 8 LinkedIn channel with rationale for use

LinkedIn	@releafcities
Why use it?	LinkedIn is now relevant for professional networking across various industries, including policy, academia, and sectors. It is useful for sharing the latest research, innovation, and project insights, as well as targeting specific communication and engagement among professionals. It also offers established networks focused on specific topics. Research projects are increasingly utilising LinkedIn to establish a presence.
Media	Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness and communicate about the project to a targeted professional audience; to expand network and stakeholders' involvement. • To showcase project update and results in a formal way. • To amplify formal project communications bi-laterally with pilot cities, project partners and individual team members.
Target Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established sectors and individual professionals in fields related to Urban ReLeaf who may benefit from project results. • Urban ReLeaf core stakeholders Academic, Research and Scientific Community, SME's and Industry, European and international networks, Environmental NGO's, EU projects and networks.
Content Structure	LinkedIn posts include text and an image; the first sentences are shown in preview and need to be clear, succinct and explain the content. Posts can link to more in-depth content.

Table 9 Twitter channel with rationale for use

Twitter	@releafcities
Why use it?	Twitter is an effective tool for quickly connecting with professionals, organizations, and researchers. Its real-time nature and wide user base make it ideal for networking and building professional stakeholder relationships. It also provides a unique opportunity to connect with individuals and groups globally.

Media	Text of up to 280 characters. This excludes media attachments (photos / images 1200 pixels by 675 pixels, videos up to 140 seconds long). Quoted tweets (displaying someone else's tweet within your own and providing a comment) can include links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness and communicate about the project in shorthand to professionals, researchers, and relevant projects. • Connect with twitter research and innovation influencers • Highlight project opportunities, activities and calls to action, and showcase project results in quick way, linking to content. • To make announcements or retweet relevant content. • Share and amplify project communications from pilot cities, and those of project partners and individual team members. • Keep track of project-relevant current issues • Track specific EU topics and project-relevant issues and engage with them
Target Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication mainly focused on researchers, professionals, innovation sector, relevant EU projects and networks • Project highlights and outputs also relevant to decision-makers and institutional representatives
Content Structure	<p>Short, direct, and engaging predominantly text and image format; include glyphs or icons</p> <p>Use twitter handles to connect with individuals, organisations, funder, and projects</p> <p>Use hashtags to index project id, keywords, topics, and networks</p> <p>Share content from other channels relevant to the project's topics.</p> <p>Insert links that redirect to more in-depth content.</p>

Table 10 YouTube channel with rationale for use

YouTube	Handle / to be determined
Why use it?	To share and store a browsable collection of project videos
Media	Video material, together with description and links
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share videos from YouTube to social media platforms. • Make recorded presentation content available to increase engagement with post event audiences • Organised content i.e., for each project's topic. • Consolidate the visual identity of the project
Target Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City Stakeholders, General public, Press and Media • Specific content will be addressed to targeted Academics, Scientists, professionals and researchers
Content Structure	<p>Video include a short video describing the project as well as interviews.</p> <p>Additional Vox pop style videos with beneficiaries i.e., participants engaged in city pilots, policy and decision-makers interested in data.</p> <p>We will also publish videos of events and presentations where appropriate.</p> <p>Text description will summarise the content, and links directing to in-depth information.</p>

Urban ReLeaf 'hub' Channels will communicate project updates, research findings, and event information from the core project activity, as well as share posts from pilot city channels about Urban ReLeaf activities. In addition to the details of content structure provided in the tables above, we will provide a content plan for communications campaigns, high level examples of which are as follows:

- Highlighting the importance of citizen-powered data ecosystems for green infrastructure planning and climate change adaptation
- Sharing project outputs, including research findings, case studies, and innovative solutions
- Promoting events, such as webinars, conferences, and workshops
- Highlighting the impact of the project on policy and practice, including political agenda-setting, cross-sectoral collaboration, and citizen engagement

Urban ReLeaf Pilot City Channels

Existing partner social media channels will share project content but also develop a bespoke communications strategy tailored to each city's specific focus, needs and timeline.

For example, in Athens, content could focus on how citizen-powered data ecosystems are being used to address air pollution and heat stress. While in Dundee, content may focus on how co-creation efforts are helping to support the quality and changes around the city's urban green space.

An example plan for the creation and sharing of content in pilot city channels is as follows:

- Sharing local city pilot updates, such as opportunities, events, case studies, and citizen engagement efforts
- Amplifying the pilot key messages and outputs with their respective communities by sharing content, and sharing it to the core project channels (and vice versa)
- Engaging with local stakeholders and citizens to promote co-creation efforts and inclusive participation
- Leveraging additional existing local social media channels and networks to reach a broader audience

We expand with one example, that is the existing twitter presence from Pilot Cities which demonstrates reach and network capacity, the rationale for connection to key stakeholders, the aims and actions as well as an outline of the content structure (Table 12).

Table 11 Pilot City Twitter Channels and reach with a plan for use

Twitter Exemplar channels and reach	Athens @cityofathens (24k followers) City of Dundee @dundeecity (16k followers) Dundee Council @dundeecouncil (35k followers) Gemeente Utrecht @GemeenteUtrecht (64k followers) Cascais: @CMCascais (4k followers) Mannheim: @mannheim_de (6.5K followers)
Why use it?	Rapidly connect with Pilot City stakeholders and their networks. In addition, with city researchers, organisations, and similar projects.
Media	Text of up to 280 characters. This excludes media attachments (photos / images 1200 pixels by 675 pixels, videos up to 140 seconds long). Quoted tweets (displaying someone else's tweet within your own and providing a comment) can include links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness and communicate about Pilot City activities to stakeholders, as well as local researchers, communities and relevant projects. • Connect with twitter influencers by location • Highlight Pilot City specific opportunities, activities and calls to action, and showcase project results in quick way, linking to content. • To make Pilot City announcements or retweet relevant content from the locale.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share and amplify core project communications, and those of project partners and individual team members. • Keep track of city-relevant current issues • Highlight relevant EU topics
Target Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication mainly focused on Pilot City Stakeholders, researchers, professionals, innovation sector, relevant EU projects and networks • Project highlights and outputs also relevant to decision-makers and institutional representatives
Content Structure	<p>Short, direct, and engaging predominantly text and image format; include glyphs or icons</p> <p>Use twitter handles to connect with individuals, organisations, funder, and projects</p> <p>Use hashtags to index project id, keywords, topics, and networks</p> <p>Share content from other channels relevant to the project's topics.</p> <p>Insert links that redirect to more in-depth content.</p>

Keywords and Hashtags Urban ReLeaf will have the same handle across all social media platforms for efficient creation and reuse of posts. The keywords are defined in the grant agreement as:

- Democratic engagement and civic participation
- Crowdsourcing
- Earth Observation / Services and applications
- Remote Sensing Instruments / Sensors
- Wearable technologies

As part of our social media strategy, we will incorporate a specific simple and accessible #hashtag in every post to enhance the overall mission of the project.

This official #hashtag, #releafcities, will create a consistent social media presence across platforms. It serves as a unique identifier for the project and establishes a connection with the message we want to promote. It is imperative that this hashtag is cascaded down and utilised on all partner social media platforms and communicated to the partner organisation's communication officers to raise brand awareness, increase Urban ReLeaf's following and enable tracking and monitoring. By implementing this strategy, we aim to establish a strong online presence and strengthen the recognition of Urban ReLeaf's mission, pilots, activities and results.

Additional #hashtags will be added as appropriate to underpin the message, an example set are as follows:

Topic: #citizenscience #naturebasedsolutions #civic #resilience #inclusive

Technology: #iot #wearables #sensor #data #datascience

Scientific: #EarthObs #GeoSpatial #remotesensing, #climatechange

Methodology: #participatory #cocreation #crowdsource #design #storytelling

Funder: #HorizonEurope #InnovateUK

2.4.3 Key Messages

Whilst we will make provision for the communication of factual information e.g., announcement of outputs, we will follow the 6W framework (see 1.4.2) to design messages and create storylines to promote an engaged and active audience to share Urban ReLeaf communications. We will create clear and concise messages that address the needs and preferences of each target audience. The messages will also be tailored to the different communication channels and platforms including traditionally hard to reach audiences. A set of key messages is outlined for each of the target audiences in Table 13 considering their needs and specifics.

Table 12 Key Messages aligned to stakeholder

Stakeholders	Example Message	Channel	Month
Academic, Research and Scientific Community	<p>Are you an architect, urban design professional or planner, or have expertise in cities, environmental science or citizen science? Join our Community of Practice for Urban design, Nature-based solutions and Blue Green Infrastructure. This international initiative will work together as part of the #UrbanReLeaf #Horizon project to create and share knowledge, best practice and innovative solutions that relate to green urban transitions, environmental and climate change issues that touch everyday lives in our cities. Further information and sign up here [URL]</p> <p>Hashtags: #urban #foresight, #environment #releafcities #citizenscience #BGI #NBS #cop #placemaking</p>	<p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Include a graphic / photograph</p> <p>To be adapted / shortened for Twitter</p>	10 - 12
City Stakeholders	<p>Exciting news! Urban ReLeaf participants co-created an inclusive participation strategy for the city of Utrecht. Follow @Releafcities to find out more and help build a citizen-powered data ecosystem for an inclusive and green transition.</p> <p>Hashtags #Releafcities #Inclusive #Citizenscience #GreenTransition #Utrecht</p> <p>Our recent workshop focused on co-defining strategies for citizens' observations on #airquality, #heatstress, #noise, #biodiversity, #well-being, and #greenspace. @releafcities aims to ensure inclusivity by engaging marginalized groups. #CitizenScience #Inclusivity #GreenPlanning #data #Utrecht</p>	<p>Twitter and image from workshop</p> <p>Tagged to city twitter handles and related accounts</p>	5
SME's and Industry	Key messages to developed aligned to data, results and innovations		18 - 48
European and	We are thrilled to announce the launch of the Urban ReLeaf Community of Practice (CoP) and its three	Website blog	10 - 12

<p>international networks, Government bodies etc</p>	<p>initial working groups! Our mission is to advance citizen-powered science as a central resource for inclusive urban green planning and policy.</p> <p>The working groups are designed to create and share best practice for innovation in public authorities bringing together citizen-powered science and Earth observation for European Green Deal and SDG 11. They will explore [ADD WG focus] These working groups will be led by ICLEI, IIASA, and UD, respectively.</p> <p>We aim to enhance visibility, strengthen mutual learning, and foster collaboration among our networks, cities, professionals, scientists' academics, civil society organizations, and related communities.</p> <p>We are currently accepting applications for the first of two open calls for participants, and we welcome all those interested in promoting sustainable urban development to join us. [Link /deadline]</p> <p>Together, we can create more inclusive, green cities that benefit everyone!</p>	<p>/newsletter item.</p> <p>LinkedIn post to be shortened for twitter and Email</p>	
<p>EU projects and networks</p>	<p>Public sector innovation in Urban ReLeaf cities is underpinned by co-creation efforts and inclusive citizen participation, as well as cutting-edge technologies supported by citizen observations. Our goal is to integrate and visualize the data in authoritative data streams and platforms.</p> <p>Hashtags #CoCreation #InclusiveParticipation #CuttingEdgeTechnology #DataIntegration #releafcities</p>	<p>Example tweet</p>	<p>10</p>
<p>Environmental NGOs and public monitoring</p>	<p>Are you interested in supporting climate change adaptation and green infrastructure planning in urban environments? Sign up for our newsletter and learn about Urban ReLeaf, a #HorizonEurope 4-year project.</p> <p>Hashtags: #ReLeafCities #UrbanReLeaf [#List cities] #Adaptation #NBS #BGI #citizenscience #citsci</p>	<p>Twitter / expanded across all social media channels</p> <p>Include Graphic Tag for relevant connections</p>	<p>7</p>
<p>The general public</p>	<p>Hello Riga Community! We're excited to announce an upcoming meeting to share with you about the Urban ReLeaf project. Our</p>	<p>Example city Cross</p>	<p>9 -18</p>

	<p>project is all about using citizen-powered activities to support urban greening for climate change adaptation.</p> <p>We're focusing on topics such as air quality, heat stress and heat islands, noise, biodiversity, well-being, and mobility [example topics to be aligned to the city focus]</p> <p>The meeting will be held at [location] on [date] at [time], and we'd love for you to join us. We're an inclusive, welcoming, and diverse community, and we want to make sure everyone feels comfortable attending. If you have particular needs to enable your attendance, please get in touch with us and let us know.</p> <p>We believe that together, we can make a real difference in our community and help create a greener, more sustainable future. So, come join us and learn more about the Urban ReLeaf project</p> <p>For more information, please visit [website or contact information]. We hope to see you there.</p>	<p>channel campaign</p> <p>Facebook / Instagram including city image / green</p> <p>general email and networks</p> <p>Print materials in local areas</p> <p>Tagged with locally relevant links</p>	
<p>Press and Media</p>	<p>Press releases generated to engage and sustain media contact</p>	<p>Project website and partner distribution</p>	<p>10 - 48</p>

Our key messages will change during the communication phases to properly address new advances and be in line with the project developments. The key messages will be translated into the different project languages and with some variation of the text permitted to align with local needs.

2.4.4 Audio Visual Materials

Our audio-visual materials include a motion designed and animated identity and an associated video to capture the concept of the project in a contemporary way. Two high quality videos for pilot cities will feature input from consortium members and city stakeholders. Together they will present the city pilot experiences from participating citizens, communities, and other actors and a documentary-style that follows the progress of the project over time, showcasing key milestones and achievements.

The **first video** will introduce the project in its early stages, this is a general-purpose overview of the project, including its goals, methodology, and expected outcomes. It will feature partner testimonials and introduce the Pilot Cities focus areas and co-design engagements with citizens.

A **second video** will be defined as pilots get underway, this is likely to take a case study approach behind the scenes of the project, showcasing the work that goes into gathering data, conducting research, and developing innovations. They will highlight citizen testimonials and

specific examples of how the project has impacted individuals, communities, authorities and decision-makers.

Additionally, **12 short videos/vox pops** will feature Urban ReLeaf events and workshops to communicate key concepts, engage stakeholders and generally present the project activities. Content for the short videos and vox pops above will be defined to explicate Urban ReLeaf development and outputs, these may include:

Technical Interactive videos that allow viewers to explore project data and findings in a dynamic and engaging way.

Animated videos to explain and simplify complex concepts and make them more accessible to a wider audience.

Webinars that provide in-depth information on specific aspects of the project, such as data collection methods or innovation development.

Social media videos will be determined in year 1, if use they will be short, shareable videos to promote the project on Facebook, Instagram and Twitter.

All videos will be promoted through the EU audio-visual channels and a dedicated Urban ReLeaf YouTube channel.

2.4.5 Online Research Dissemination Platforms

Online research dissemination platforms have become increasingly important for sharing research and innovation outputs with a wider audience. Urban ReLeaf's aim to maximize the visibility and impact of our outputs, while also ensuring that they are accessible and understandable to a diverse audience. In this context, our dissemination log includes a publications area, we will develop a comprehensive plan that includes clear objectives, target audiences, content creation, dissemination channels, for the exploitation of outputs. We will report on the metrics for evaluating the success of the strategy as part of Deliverable 6.3.

An indication of target dissemination platforms where we will actively share outcomes and results is as follows:

- **Research and Innovation Success Stories** <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories>
- **Cordis** <https://cordis.europa.eu/en>
- **Horizon Results Booster** <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/d-e-booster>
- **Horizon Dashboard** <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>
- **Innovation Radar** <https://www.innoradar.eu/>
- **Open Aire** <https://www.openaire.eu/>
- **Zenodo** <https://zenodo.org/>
- **Partner research organisations** repositories
- **Individual Researcher accounts** e.g., ORCID <https://orcid.org/>
- **Research Gate** (social networking for research outputs) <https://www.researchgate.net/>

3 Part 3: Measuring the Impact of Communication, Engagement, Dissemination

3.1 Internal communications

Communication among partners is crucial to exchange up-to-date information, knowledge and data on what is going on in the different WPs and to enhance and optimise external communication and dissemination. Internal communication will be ensured through regular exchange of information via a dedicated MS Teams channel, e-mail and during scheduled meetings, when all partners gather to discuss achievements, upcoming activities, deadlines, and issues arising within the different work packages.

A link to the Dissemination log is a standing item on monthly consortium agendas as a prompt for partners to complete. WP (Work Package) leaders also communicate key research outputs during Consortium meetings and other WP leader meetings that are organised when needed.

While some partners (IIASA and UD) are directly involved in communication activities in view of their role in the project, all partners are requested to regularly participate in communication and dissemination activities, namely:

- In the case of Pilot Cities, developing a local communication plan and stakeholder engagement strategy based on the Urban ReLeaf Communications pack.
- Communicating their activities and disseminating their results to their respective networks, on social media and through news on the project website using project and their own online channels,
- Informing the other partners of interesting, related initiatives and events they could participate in,
- Keeping track of their communication and dissemination activities by filling in a dedicated dissemination log (Figure 10) available in the project SharePoint,
- Disseminating results and publications through open access repositories OPENAIRE, Zenodo and institutional repositories as outlined in section 2.4.2.

Dissemination and Communication activities. List only activities directly linked to the project.									
PARTNER (S)	TYPE (list)	START DATE dd/mm/yyyy	END DATE dd/mm/yyyy	EVENT	PRESENCE (list)	CITY	COUNTRY	EDI Checklist	
IIASA	Participation in a Conference	7/12/2022	9/12/2022	EuroGEO Workshop - Session on CS uptake in official data	PHYSICAL	ATHENS	GREECE		
IIASA	Website	11/1/2023	n/a	Project page on IIASA website	ONLINE				
IIASA	Press release	25/01/2023	25/01/2023	Press release announcing the project kick-off at IIASA	ONLINE				
IIASA	Participation in a Workshop	24/01/2023	24/01/2023	Presentation at the CitiObs kick-off meeting	ONLINE				
IIASA	Participation in a Workshop	20/02/2023	20/02/2023	Presentation at the GREENGAGE kick-off meeting	ONLINE				
UD	Press release	6/2/2023	6/2/2023	Press release announcing the project kick-off at Dundee	ONLINE			UK	
UD	Participation in a Workshop	9/2/2023	9/2/2023	Green Health & Wellbeing Partnership Relaunch workshop in Dundee	PHYSICAL	Dundee		UK	
UD	Participation in a Conference	7/3/2023	7/3/2023	IVING STREETS SCOTLAND BIG WALKING SEMINAR- delivering a keynote talk for 100 participants	PHYSICAL	STIRLING		UK	
UD	Organisation of a Conference	21/02/2023	21/04/2024	European i-Tree Eco conference for 2024	ONLINE	Dundee		UK	
UD	Participation in a Workshop	27/02/2023	27/02/2023	Exploratory Discussion with Council Leaders and NGOs on Dundee as a NbS City	PHYSICAL	Dundee		UK	
UD	Brokerage Event	1/3/2023	1/3/2023	with Dundee Naturalists Association as a celebration year for 2024 to be a 'Lets get wild in Dundee'	PHYSICAL	Dundee		UK	
UD	Organisation of a Conference	1/3/2023	24/03/2023	Feeding Tayside through the climate crisis Conference - With Bioregioning Tayside	ONLINE	Dundee		UK	
UD	Website	2/3/2023	n/a	Project page on University of Dundee website	ONLINE	Dundee		UK	
VUB	nt other than a Conference or a Workshop	28/03/2023	n/a	ziveness, Equity and Diversity' - Discussion about inclusive communication materials and policies	ONLINE				
IIASA	nt other than a Conference or a Workshop	11/4/2023	11/4/2023	station on 'Climate change adaptation and mitigation: The ADAP+UHI and Urban ReLeaf projects'	ONLINE		VIENNA	AT	
UD	Participation in a Conference	24/03/2023	24/03/2024	Feeding Tayside through the climate crisis Conference - UD with Bioregioning Tayside & Partners	PHYSICAL	Dundee		UK	
UD	Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	7/3/2023	7/3/2023	National TV segment. Interview Urban ReLeaf Mel Woods and Friends on the Earth Tayside	ONLINE		n/a	UK	
IIASA	Participation in a Conference	19/4/2023	20/4/2023	stentale für bürger*innenbasierte Datenströme und neue Formen urbaner Entscheidungsfindung	PHYSICAL	Linz		AT	
UD	Organisation of a Workshop	21/4/2023	21/4/2023	British Council Earth Scholarship 2023 Day 5 Workshop	PHYSICAL	Dundee		UK	

Figure 10 Dissemination Log, Communication Activities, Event Schedule and Publications (number and types of audiences are included but cannot be seen in the screen capture)

The involvement of all partners in the communication and dissemination activities will ensure the project to be more widely promoted, to reach a wider audience and ultimately, to have a wider impact.

3.2 Tracking and Monitoring

Our communication strategy is designed to ensure that our messaging is effective and impactful, and that we can measure and evaluate our performance in an effective way. To achieve this, we will be using a range of analytical tools to monitor and track our progress using quantitative measures e.g., monitoring traffic via the project website WordPress platform. In addition, we will also be utilising integrated systems to manage our social media presence such as Hootsuite, which will allow us to streamline our social media activity and ensure that our messaging and tracking is consistent across all channels.

We will actively be seeking out stakeholder feedback, both online and in person, to gain a deeper understanding of our audience and their needs. By monitoring engagement and responses using qualitative approaches e.g., feedback from films and blogs, event and activities, and other key metrics, we will be able to identify areas of strength and weakness in our strategy and make data-driven decisions to improve our overall performance. By systematically tracking and collecting this feedback, we will be able to continually improve and refine our communication strategy over time.

We aim for a target of a 50% minimum share of female participants, and 30-40% marginalized and vulnerable groups (e.g., elderly, or young people who are vulnerable to heat induced stress). The specific monitoring of the special engagement focus in WP6 will be delivered as part of Task 6.5

Table 14, below, outlines both quantitative and qualitative measures of performance, and metrics are defined with this in mind. Starting from the overall WP6 objectives, the main indicators identified can be grouped and initially developed based on:

Table 13 ECD outputs with indicative questions and related qualitative and quantitative metric

Output Type	Questions	Metrics (Quantitative and Qualitative)
Communication	Have targeted audiences responded through chosen channels?	Number of followers on social media platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, etc.) used to promote the project.
	How well do the brand design materials reinforce the project concept and values?	Number of website views and unique visitors. Number of project and pilot media mentions and press coverage, including online and offline media outlets.
	Do the events and communications meet ethical standards, data governance principles,	Number of localised online features via city websites and social media channels

	<p>gender equality, inclusiveness and green values?</p>	<p>Perception of the project's brand identity by stakeholders.</p> <p>Perception of the project values and inclusiveness by relevant stakeholders.</p>
<p>Engagement</p>	<p>How effective were the relationships with key stakeholders and networks in creating visibility and leveraging awareness for Urban ReLeaf activities?</p> <p>Do the events and activities meet project objectives for audience types and gender</p> <p>Did the RRI guidelines contribute to the success of the project?</p>	<p>Number of likes, mentions, shares, and retweets of stories, blogs etc on social media channels.</p> <p>Number of newsletter subscribers and open rates.</p> <p>Number of events and activities organized, and the attendance rate</p> <p>Number of collaboration and partnership opportunities generated through the project.</p> <p>% gender identity at events and activities</p> <p>Perceived level of engagement and satisfaction of stakeholders with the project's activities and outputs.</p> <p>Perception of the project's ethical and data governance principles by stakeholders.</p> <p>Perception of inclusiveness and gender equality in the project's activities by stakeholders.</p> <p>Feedback from engagement measures e.g., pop up community labs, insight workshop on the relevance and quality of the activities and outcomes.</p>
<p>Dissemination</p>	<p>How many people have been reached through the dissemination activities of the Urban ReLeaf project?</p> <p>How many publications or media outlets have featured the project's activities and outcomes?</p> <p>How many key results were exploited?</p>	<p>The dissemination rate for Urban ReLeaf results</p> <p>Number of downloads of project materials, such as reports, white papers, or presentations.</p> <p>Number of attendees at events, workshops, and webinars organized by the project team.</p> <p>Feedback from stakeholders, including collaborators, partners, and participants, on the quality and relevance of scientific results, project deliverables and publications events.</p> <p>Case studies and success stories of how the project's activity and outputs have impacted on the community and been used by stakeholders</p>

		and generated impact and the platforms they feature on.
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The communications reliant on partner organisations in the Pilot Cities playing a key role in creating and disseminating our messages to a wider audience. The communications team will rely on our pilot cities to utilise their existing communication channels and tools to reach their respective audiences effectively. To ensure comprehensive data collection, relevant project partners will be responsible for monitoring inputs and tracking feedback, which will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of our communication strategy and help us achieve our Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This approach allows us to make any necessary adjustments to the strategy to ensure that we achieve our desired outcomes. The success of our project depends on effective communication, and we are committed to implementing a robust and collaborative approach to achieve our goals.

3.2.1 Impact Indicators and KPIs

For measuring effectiveness, the following KPIs and related numbers have been foreseen in the Description of Action. These targets are either delivered or supported through monitoring of communications and engagement as part of the engagement, communication and dissemination plan (Table 15).

Table 14 Selected KPI's supported by the Engagement, Communication and Dissemination plan

KPI.	Description	Target
1	No. of citizens to be mobilized	250 -1500/city
2	No. of cities to be recruited through accelerator programme	10
3	Minimum share of women participants in campaigns	50%
4	Share of participants from vulnerable/marginalized groups across city pilots	30-40%
9	No. of stakeholders participating in co-design workshops	75-120 total; 12-20/city
14	No. of participants in Design for Business sprints, Pop-up community and culture labs	DfB:20-30/city; Pop-up Labs 30-40/city
20	No. of visitors to Urban ReLeaf online presence & social media	Y1: 10,000+; Y2:50,000+; Y3: 100,000+; Y4: 200,000+

4 Conclusion

In summary, our strategy for communications is initiated at a time of rapidly changing offline and online behaviours, best practices, technologies and platforms. Reaching and engaging different stakeholders in a meaningful way requires an increasingly sophisticated approach.

The Urban ReLeaf ECD Plan is a comprehensive and co-designed strategy that outlines the steps for Urban ReLeaf to engage with a range of stakeholders, with a particular focus on inclusion and reaching a diversity of people, and to communicate effectively about the project. The implementation of the strategy in Phase 1 of the project will necessarily change and adapt the outline communication plan as we rapidly take into account localised Pilot City needs and stakeholders to Month 12, and in the second phase where Pilot City Campaigns are launched. We will monitor our progress through Key Performance Indicators with a focus on meaningful engagement through the sharing of stories and iterate our approach to the strategy where necessary, reporting in Month 28, to maximize the impact of the project.

Moving forward and in preparation for the follow-on Deliverable 6.4, we will monitor and reflect on the challenges faced and how were they addressed; how the Communications, Engagement and Dissemination plan was applied; and what lessons we learned from the Communications Strategy, and how can they be applied to the second and final phases of Urban ReLeaf.